

MACHINE-DRIVEN EXPERIMENTATION FOR SOLVING CHALLENGING CONSOLIDATION PROBLEMS

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ABSTRACT

The paper presents a new modelling concept for characterisation of the consolidation in composite precursors. Consolidation is a central process in composites manufacturing, it affects defects formation, dimensional tolerances and the final quality of the composite part. Due to the nonlinear and coupled nature of the process the characterisation of consolidation is a nontrivial task. The proposed concept of the consolidation sensor is not limited by a subjective judgement about material behavior from the experimental testing. It is capable of designing loading programmes and distinguishing between dominant deformation mechanisms rather than imposing rigid framework of arbitrarily selected consolidation models. The sensor is self-developing, adaptable and capable of capturing the main characteristics of the consolidation process by interrogating the material in the way it independently decides. The proposed system is set to recognise the flow/deformation modes by their characteristic signatures and make an assumption about the current flow mode during the test. The consolidation sensor was validated against a number of different phenomenological models.

1 INTRODUCTION

Consolidation in composite manufacturing presents a serious challenge for defect mitigation, predicting dimensional tolerances, and optimization of composite morphology due to nonlinearity of all the flow and deformation processes involved in it. These processes might occur on multiple scales and include various mechanisms of different nature, such as percolation flow, shear flow, reinforcement compaction, inter-ply and intra-ply void suppression, etc. Each of these processes involves a large number of material parameters required to describe it and significant stochastic variation of them [1], [2], [3].

Coupling and the concurrent nature of the processes in consolidation make material modelling and material characterisation non-trivial. For a given temperature, model parameters include the constants of viscosity models (of resin, tows, and plies as functions of fibre volume fraction, strain rates), components of permeability tensors (as functions of fibre volume fraction, saturation), ply interaction parameters (in time-dependent adhesion and friction models), parameters for fibre bed response models, surface tension, parameters describing initial state of material, etc. The situation gets an extra dimension of complexity when non-isothermal and heat transfer processes come into play. A fully coupled description may involve a dozen of separate constitutive equations with tens of parameters that need to be determined in separate tests, where each factor is carefully isolated

Experimental characterisation to determine material parameters for each of these constitutive equations require multiple explicit and implicit assumption on how material deforms and flows. There are various testing strategies introduced for consolidation assessment, material extraction, and model

validation. These strategies vary for different materials and assume dominant mode of deformation [1], [3], [4], [5]. Such strategies can include displacement or load controlled ramp-dwell programmes, monotonic loading at various strain-rates etc.

Since different models demand different characterisation strategies, there is no universal procedure for assessment of composite precursors' behaviour. Loading programmes are predefined before the actual testing and their validity is hard to prove in particular for complex systems where flow transition and flow combination is observed [6]. Making assumptions on how material is supposed to behave is often based on experience and only justified by a limited number of validation tests.

Figure 1: Micrographs of a cross-ply [90/0]₈ specimen (a) and a blocked ply [90₄/0₄]₂ specimen(b). Both shear and percolation flows are present simultaneously [1].

The current project is focused on a different philosophy of modelling. This paper explores the feasibility of removing a subjective judgement about material behavior from experimental testing and attempts to address this problem more efficiently.

2 FLOW MODELS

Depending on applied manufacturing conditions, fibrous network and viscous matrix of a composite precursor might exhibit various flow and deformation mechanisms [6], [7]. The possible flow mode depends on a number of factors, such as applied pressure value and rate, constraints of the composite precursor, fibre volume fraction, resin viscosity and other material parameters.

Additionally, flow modes might take place at various material scales, e.g. intra-tow, macro-scale, through thickness percolation flow, shear of individual flows or inter ply resin filaments

As a starting point two major flow modes are considered. One such flow mode is a bleeding or percolation flow, when resin bleeds out from the laminate along the fibres with limited through thickness movement. In this case fibres are not shifted in plane by the resin and the deformation is limited by the fibre bed response [8], [9]. This deformation mode is typical for low-viscosity thermoset resins.

Another example is a shear or squeezing flow, where resin pushes fibres transversely to the fibre and compaction directions. In this case the system deforms as an incompressible fluid [10], [11]. Such deformation mode is mostly observed in consolidation of thermoplastic prepregs.

Above mentioned flow mechanisms might coexist within the same manufacturing process. For example, in the beginning resin flows transversely to fibres in a shear manner, but after fulfilling certain criteria [1] the flow transforms to percolation and resin bleeds out.

Understanding of the flow deformation mechanism during consolidation is crucial. For example, elevated temperature of the manufacturing process may prevent resin from filling all possible gaps between tows, due to resin bleeding instead of pushing fibres in a transverse direction and filling those gaps. On the contrary, low temperatures may require high levels of pressure in order to achieve a target thickness and fibre volume fraction.

Several major consolidation models are considered in this paper. These models are included in the model's library of the proposed consolidation sensor in a form of governing differential equations.

2.1 Shear flow

Several cases of a shear flow depending on the boundary conditions and contact region type are described by Rogers [11]. The model for the shear flow was obtained for highly anisotropic incompressible viscous fluids. In order to illustrate the solution for the practical case this model was applied to the problem of the transverse flow of the fluid, which is squeezed between two rigid plates.

It was shown that constitutive equations for different types of shear flows depend on the friction conditions on the boundary between the rigid compression plate and the surface of the composite precursor and the contact region

Thus, resulting governing equations (mass balance, constitutive equations for Newtonian anisotropic fluid, boundary conditions) can be condensed to an expression linking tow thickness (h), tow width (w), rate of thickness change (\dot{h}), and applied pressure (P_{applied}) represented as follows:

No slip boundary condition, constant contact region (henceforth referred to as "flow 1"):

$$\dot{h} = \frac{P_{\text{applied}}}{4\eta} h \quad (1)$$

No slip boundary condition, varying contact region (henceforth referred to as "flow 2"):

$$\dot{h} = \frac{P_{\text{applied}}}{4\eta h_0} h^2 \quad (2)$$

No friction boundary condition, constant contact region (henceforth referred to as "flow 3"):

$$\dot{h} = \frac{P_{\text{applied}}}{\eta h_0 (w^2 + 3h^2)} h^4 \quad (3)$$

No friction boundary condition, varying contact region (henceforth referred to as "flow 4"):

$$\dot{h} = \frac{P_{\text{applied}}}{\eta h_0 (w_0^2 h_0^2 + 3h^4)} h^6 \quad (4)$$

Where h_0 – initial thickness, w_0 – initial width, η – effective viscosity of the tape.

2.2 Percolation flow

Darcy's law is used to describe movement of resin through a still network of fibres [10], [12]. In the case when fluid motion is driven by through-thickness compaction, i.e. closing mould, rate independent component (fibre bed response) is introduced to link operating pressure and fibre volume fraction evolution [13]. Under assumption that flow is possible only in-plane of the laminate, Darcy flow, fibre bed response and momentum balance lead to a model showing gradual pressure distribution from resin to fibre network during compaction process (henceforth referred to as "flow 5"):

$$\dot{h} = \frac{3K(h)}{\eta w^2} (P_{\text{applied}} - P_{\text{res}}(h))h \quad (5)$$

Where permeability parameter $K(h)$ is calculated according to [8] and fibre bed response P_{res} according to [9][13].

The fibre permeability is not constant over the process, it is a function of a fibre volume fracture (V_f), fibre radius (r_f) and layup architecture constant (k_0).

$$K = \frac{r_f^2 (1 - V_f)^3}{4k_0 V_f^2} \quad (6)$$

Since volume fraction significantly changes within the compaction of the material, it directly affects the permeability of the composite precursor.

Another feature of the percolation model is a consideration of the fibre deformation behaviour instead of treatment fibres as separate layers. In such an approach fibre-to-fibre contact is assumed. The region of each fibre between two neighbouring contact points is represented as a small beam. During consolidation as fibres are pushed closer to each other, the length of these beams reduces. Thus, the bending stiffness increases significantly which causes nonlinear deformation response.

A model for the fibre bed response was proposed by Gutowski [13]

$$P_{res} = \sigma_A \frac{\sqrt{V/V_f} - 1}{\left(\sqrt{V_{lim}/V} - 1\right)^4} \quad (7)$$

Where σ_A is an empirical material constant.

2.3 DefGen model

Above-mentioned shear and percolation flow models are based on incompatible assumptions in terms of compressibility and fibre displacement. Both flow models are applied to different types of composite precursors. But in certain cases, they might coexist within one consolidation process, e.g., it was demonstrated by Hubert [4] that both shear and percolation flows can act concurrently.

In order to describe flow mode transition, a new phenomenological consolidation model for toughened prepregs is proposed by Belnoue et al [1].

In the proposed model the apparent viscosity presented as a product of strain rate and strain dependent terms. The strain dependent term is in turn is a product of terms accounting for deformation at ply (macro) and micro levels.

$$\sigma = \eta_{micro}(\varepsilon)\eta_{ply}(\varepsilon)\eta_{rate}(\dot{\varepsilon})\dot{\varepsilon} \quad (8)$$

Where $\eta_{micro}(\varepsilon)$ is the micro level strain dependent term, $\eta_{ply}(\varepsilon)$ is the ply level strain dependent term, $\eta_{rate}(\dot{\varepsilon})$ is the strain rate term, $\varepsilon = \ln(h/h_0)$ is the Hencky measure of strain, and σ is the applied pressure. A precise description of these terms can be found in [1].

Since all of the previously considered models are represented in terms of thickness rate instead of deformation, the previous equation is reformulated:

$$\dot{h} = - \frac{a+1}{\sqrt{\eta_{micro} \cdot \eta_{ply} \cdot \eta_{rate}}} \cdot \frac{P_{applied}}{h} \quad (9)$$

Where $\overline{\eta_{micro}} = \frac{\eta_{micro}}{\eta_{resin}}$, $\overline{\eta_{rate}} = e^b$ Material parameters a and b can be found in [1].

In DefGen model the transition from squeezing to percolation flow occurs when the deformation reaches its critical value. It is assumed that during compaction the upper fibre moves towards the fibre below pushing the resin in the transverse direction. When neighbouring fibres come into contact and form a column it locks the shear driven flow. At this point resin starts bleeding along the fibres, which is one of the key features of a percolation flow.

3 CONSOLIDATION SENSOR

The schematic representation of the proposed consolidation sensor is shown in Figure 2. During the characterisation experiment a composite precursor is subjected to compression in the testing rig. At each load step the machine captures thickness evolution of the laminate. Then the collected feedback is passed on to the consolidation sensor.

After that the sensor starts interrogating each consolidation model from the material library in order to define the degree of similarity with a feedback loop and the required model parameters e.g. viscosity, permeability constants etc. At this point the system conducts ranking of the possible flow models to define which one produces the best results.

At the end of each load step consolidation sensor passes the obtained results to the load schedule picking module, which provides the compression testing rig with the loading schedule for the next step. Such a loading schedule is defined in a way to distinguish between candidate models with a higher resolution.

Figure 2: Schematic representation of the proposed testing setup.

Normally, the testing program is predefined before the experiment and standard compression machines do not provide an option to alter load schedule real-time during the test. For this reason, a new testing rig is being build.

In advance of actual material testing, the proof of concept is tested against a virtual complex material. An extensively validated model of toughened prepreg is set in the module referred to as “BlackBox” with predefined processing parameters. Processing parameters and material model is not visible from the processing module and it is up to the designed consolidation sensor to investigate it.

More detailed algorithm of the system is presented in Figure 3.

At the beginning of each load steps the BlackBox receives a load schedule as an input parameter. Using this, along with the material model, it is now possible to solve the governing differential equation of the target consolidation model for a given timestep. After adding a noise component to the solution, resulting curve similar to the real experimental data is produced as an output of the BlackBox module.

Now it is up to the consolidation sensor to study the produced feedback and evaluate available models on the degree of similarity. At the beginning the noisy output thickness curve is approximated by nonparametric spline regression method. This method is chosen over more simple existing parametric solutions, like polynomial regression or Fourier transform, because the sensor should not use any restricting assumptions about deformation behavior.

After the approximation is conducted, the resulting smooth curve is differentiated in order to obtain a function for thickness rate in a similar way it is represented in a governing equation.

The next step for the sensor is to interrogate consolidation models from the library and to characterise the Blackbox’s output. In order to do that there is a special submodule inside the consolidation sensor referred to as “Processing” module.

The purpose of the Processing module is to estimate the capability of the chosen consolidation

model from the library to describe the obtained feedback from the hardware. In other words, it conducts parametric regression using a governing equation for a candidate flow model as a fitting function. At this step the optimal set of model parameters is defined.

Figure 3: Detailed algorithm of the consolidation sensor.

Since there are several consolidation models in the library, there is a need to analyse each one of them. Therefore, there is one Processing module for each flow mode described in the library as a part of a consolidation sensor. Each of these modules produces its own estimation of truthfulness for the corresponding flow mode.

The last action of the sensor at the current load step is to conduct models ranking. It compares the root mean square error for each Processing module's regression output and picks the best performing model. At this step the Processing module takes into consideration both the instant and all of the previously collected loading history. This is done to capture characteristic signatures of the flow model which might occur only during the current loading step and are not recognisable at previous ones. At the same time the set of model parameters is passed further to the load schedule picking module.

This module analyses possible load paths for the next load steps. The goal is to pick loading schedule which will produce the maximum difference between candidate models from the library. It will allow consolidation sensor to distinguish between candidates in the most effective way.

The estimation gets refined as more and more data are acquired during this step-by-step procedure.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

At this stage of the research there are three main objectives for the consolidation sensor. It must be capable of identifying and characterising both shear and percolation phenomenological models inside of the BlackBox as well as locating the transition point from one flow mode to another.

There are two ways to define flow transition inside the BlackBox module. The first option is to set a switch which will substitute initial flow model for the subsequent one at the predefined moment of time. According to the flow transition mechanism described in the previous section, the starting flow model is a shear flow model. The subsequent one is a percolation model.

Another way to introduce flow transition is to put DefGen model inside the BlackBox, where such mechanism is activated automatically when deformation criteria is met.

The proposed concept was tested against each of these cases in order to prove its validity and robustness.

The consolidation sensor successfully pre-processed an input data coming from the BlackBox. It managed to filter a noise component in a thickness evolution curve without any prior knowledge about the studied model and to capture the characteristic signatures of the process, such as sudden changes of a thickness rate behavior, which might be the sign of flow transition or compression load increase. It is important particular to the real experiment, where the received data coming from the hardware is noisy.

In order to locate the flow transition point, the sensor runs analysis in two different ways simultaneously. The first approach is to take into account the whole load-history curve to take advantage of all the collected data. It helps to refine the prediction and make the algorithm more robust and reliable.

The second approach is to consider only the current step's feedback to locate sudden instantaneous changes in consolidation model's behaviour. This is done because in case of abnormalities the regression fit will be influenced by the data collected in the previous steps and won't be able to detect the transition point.

The first test was conducted to characterise shear flow model hidden inside the BlackBox.

Figure 4: Root mean square error for each load step of the process.

As shown in Figure 4, one of the candidate shear models produces significantly lower RMSE value, which indicates, that the flow was characterised successfully.

The goal for another test case was to analyse percolation flow model inside the BlackBox.

Figure 5: Detailed algorithm of the consolidation sensor.

Similar to the previous test case a percolation candidate model performed with the lowest RMSE

proving that the consolidation sensor can detect bleeding flows successfully. The error produced by flow 1 and flow 2 models is too high, and it's not shown on the graph due to scale reasons. The results are presented in Figure 5.

The last test case was to identify two stages of the consolidation and the moment of transition from one to another.

All load history considered

Only current load step considered

Figure 6: Detailed algorithm of the consolidation sensor.

As shown in Figure 6, the framework successfully identifies the squeezing and percolation stages of the process as well as the flow transition point. At first shear flow models perform with a less error value until the transition point is reached (time interval 40-49 sec). After the transition occurred the best performing shear model starts decreasing the degree of similarity in the load-history approach graph. Instant load step approach at this stage shows sudden change in the models' behaviour, which indicates that flow transition has occurred.

As a result of the characterisation study of the flow transition process a new synthetic model is obtained. This model is represented as a combination of simpler models from the material library for each load step of the compaction. Additionally, it contains information about the flow transition point of the consolidation process.

The next stage of the research is to test the synthetic model against a well-proven phenomenological model, such as DefGen model. The idea of the test is to define an arbitrary loading schedule beforehand and to feed it to both the synthetic and DefGen models. After that the feedback of these models is to be compared in order to estimate the consolidation sensor's capability to produce robust response for any given pre-defined loading.

The current results show that for low a load rate the current number of phenomenological models in the library is insufficient. The synthetic model's output shows discrepancies with DefGen model for a longer shear flow stage, which happens in case of a slow loading. Besides that, there is a need for the flow transition criteria to be evaluated at the stage of the initial testing. The consolidation sensor should be able to derive the criteria based on the characterisation tests' results and the preliminary flow models allocation for each load step.

The possible solution for the abovementioned problems is to expand the existing models' library and to add flow transition criteria estimation as a part of the consolidation sensor's routine. The work to add these features to the existing consolidation sensor's structure is currently in progress.

9 CONCLUSIONS

A new consolidation sensor framework for resin flow in composite precursors was developed. It was tested against several phenomenological models. The results proved the proposed concept and sensors ability to conduct characterisation without any prior knowledge about the studied model.

Unlike existing characterisation techniques, the new framework is not limited by the pre assumed deformation modes. It designs a loading schedule program real-time based on the experiment output to distinguish between the possible candidate models. Such a result would not be achievable if the

loading schedule was predefined beforehand without taking into the consideration the characteristic signatures of the process.

The consolidation sensor was able to reveal shear and percolation flow stages as well as a point of transition from one flow to another. Further studies aiming to prove the proposed concept on a compression testing rig are currently in progress.

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